

TOURISM AFTER CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC - WAY FORWARD FOR TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY IN THE UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

A coronavirus infection was confirmed in China in January 2020. After two years of the pandemic, countries are still dealing with new virus variants, fifth and sixth waves differing degrees of success in vaccinating their national populations during two years. And this paper looks into research questions by comparing the effects of international travel on the private sector before and after COVID-19. The article recommended qualitative research methodologies as an analytical technique to gather information from workers in the tourism industry. Through online questionnaire surveys, the respondents' opinions were gathered and also future traveler arrivals and people's desire for particular tourist destinations has taken into account.

INTRODUCTION

Many nations around the world have highlighted the phenomenon of tourism as a means of generating income, and significant investments are made in this field. Many tourists are interested in this type of industrial tourism. Geographical features, topography, climate, and location are crucial components of tourist attractions that contribute significantly to the social and economic advancement of numerous areas.

Though, with careful management, tourism can have positive socio-economic effects as well as negative ones. It has historically played a significant and positive role in society. When it comes to its economic impact, the tourism industry is large and expanding at a quick speed. In addition to contributing 10% of the world GDP and 5% of carbon dioxide emissions, tourism is the third-largest industry in the world. As the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), there is an anticipated 74% decrease in tourist arrivals in 2020 when compared to 2019. In the Asia-Pacific and Western Hemisphere, the effects have been especially bad for numerous developing countries, especially the small island states (Apriyanti, 2023). Restrictions on international travel have been implemented by many governments worldwide as one of the key policy initiatives to stop the COVID-19 outbreak (Ranasinghe et al., 2020). Travel restrictions outside of the country, however, have been extraordinary and have primarily decrease the travel and tourism sector (Nhamo et al., 2020). According to Merwe et al. (2021), some examples of restrictions include closed borders for non-

citizens and non-residents, partial border closures that restrict entry from particular countries, or closing borders altogether. Other restrictions include arrival quarantines and health certificate requirements. Consequently, most operations pertaining to foreign tourism have ceased.

Travel restrictions, lockdowns, quarantines, and required testing have all had an impact on national tourism systems, depending on the circumstance. This has led to unstable and unpredictable business and travel environments. Among the noteworthy developments on the demand side were the shift of business travelers to videoconferencing, as well as the readiness of large segments of the populace in industrialized nations to take domestic vacations in the acknowledged lack of alternatives (Adinolfi et al., 2020; Jacobsen et al., 2021). International travel was difficult and time-consuming due to quarantines, test requirements, and travel restrictions. As money stayed in national economies, markets benefited, but travel destinations suffered.

There are more important lessons to be learned in addition to this more detailed account of the crisis and its effects. COVID-19 should be viewed as an analog of climate change, as has been suggested previously (Gossling et al., 2021) and reiterated by others (Cole & Dodds, 2021; Prideaux et al., 2020; Sigala, 2020). There are some distinctions: although climate change has been recognized as a persistent threat for decades, the pandemic broke out in a matter of months. While the effects of climate change have primarily had local or regional significance, such as in the context of flooding events, storms, wildfires, or heat waves, the effects of COVID-19 were felt immediately on a global scale (UNCCS, 2019). There are similarities, though.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Different nations are at different stages of the COVID-19 crisis management process. While some are modifying their policies to fill in the gaps and meet the needs of their tourism industries, others are realizing that they must begin putting together extensive plans for the industry's recovery. Although the focus in recent months has rightly been on safeguarding employees and tourists as well as assisting in the survival of businesses, policymakers are also taking into account the crisis' longer-term effects on the industry and the structural changes that will be required to create a stronger, more resilient, and sustainable tourism economy in the future (McCartney, 2021).

Travelers' movements have been impacted globally by emergency protocols and restrictions put in place by tourist destinations. Transit between regions was severely restricted, and people's movements were stopped (Nagaj and Zuromskaite, 2021). Towns were empty, people's movements had stopped, and beaches and resorts were in ruins. Both the global economy and people's means of subsistence have been impacted by the COVID-19-induced worldwide quarantine. In the meantime, Anca Antoaneta

(Vărzaru et al., 2021) looks into how the COVID-19 pandemic has affected the travel and tourism industry as well as the overall economy. Based on the research findings and exploratory literature research, the article synthesized various approaches to guarantee the tourism sector's resilience during the COVID-19 pandemic phase.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The goal of this study is to investigate the potential future changes in the relationship between COVID-19 and the tourism industry. Given how many facets of social and economic life have been impacted by the epidemic, that many greater numbers of stories published about its effects in various parts of the world. The possible global ramifications of the COVID-19 pandemic are widely covered by almost any internet news source (Zhang and Hayashi, 2022). When it comes to learning about the effects of the pandemic, tourism is one of the primary focal points. After this data was analyzed, assessments were conducted using the likely effects of the pandemic on tourism over short, medium, and long terms. The many circumstances pertaining to the private tourism sector are analyzed through a survey. Employing, Stay at Home (ST), Boom and Recovery (BR), Spread of Virus (SOV), Transportation Pattern (TP), and Visitors Safe (VS) as well. To examine the risk assessment of COVID-19 for tourism management, a series of questions were posed to the respondents. The achievements are discussed in the sections that follow.

Total Coronavirus Cases in Uzbekistan

Active Cases in Uzbekistan

Total Coronavirus Deaths in Uzbekistan

International tourism, expenditures for passenger transport items (current US\$)- Uzbekistan

International tourism, expenditures (% of total imports) - Uzbekistan

International tourism, receipts (% of total exports) - Uzbekistan

International tourism, number of arrivals - Uzbekistan

International tourism, number of departures

RESULTS AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

	COVID-19 (observed)	Unabated climate change (anticipated)
Biophysical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leisure-related pressure on ecosystems grows Loss of income for protected areas in emerging economies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Loss of entire ecosystems (e.g., coral reefs) Loss of assets (e.g., snow) Increase in disruptive extreme events
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business disruptions, bankruptcy New debt Domestic & inter-regional tourism Rise in gig-economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Socioeconomic destabilization of countries "Tourism corridors" between stable regions Carbon price creates new tourism geography Specific tourism models no longer viable Loss of infrastructure (e.g., sea level rise)
Social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Travel restrictions Lock-downs Increase in use of virtual travel products & gaming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social divide leads to destabilization Internat. tourism seizes in many countries Virtual travel gains importance Cruises as safe forms of tourism (?) Metaverse as escape for the masses (?)
Political	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong state Surveillance structures Polarization in and radicalization of civil society ('antivaxxers') Rebound-priority 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Semi-permeable borders Nation states focused on internal struggles Law & order priority Diverging agendas in regard to climate change mitigation

Statistics Agency: In January-November 2023, 55.7 thousand (<https://repost.uz/sosed-tolko-tak-zaglyadivayut>) foreign citizens visited Uzbekistan for the purpose of treatment.

- The citizens who most often entered Uzbekistan were:
 - Tajikistan - 39.2 thousand people;
 - Kazakhstan - 9.9 thousand people;
 - Kyrgyzstan - 4.9 thousand people;
 - other countries – 1.7 thousand people.

In the linear scale above illustrated the amount of total coronavirus cases in Uzbekistan from 2020 up to 2023. The cases moderately grew up from very beginning up to current moment. The number of infected people saw fluctuation with different numbers. It grew up its top in 2022 on February with more than 15 000 infected patients. It is interesting to note that there are more patients who has infected with coronavirus current years that the data stayed the same from may 2023. When it comes to the amount of total coronavirus deaths in Uzbekistan showed its peak point in 2022 on march with 1637 deaths and it remained the same for the rest of the given period.

Rebuilding stakeholder and visitor confidence in the tourism sector is the first step towards revitalizing the industry. Governments need to restore public confidence in the company through public relations campaigns. Operatives, the government, and donor organizations must work together to fulfill the industry's financial commitments following the lockdown. Here, cooperation should extend beyond money to include exchanging concepts and tactics for enhancing the sector and surviving in the face of upcoming difficulties. Based on the findings, policy initiatives aimed at strengthening the travel and tourism industry may play a significant role in revitalizing the global economy following the COVID-19 pandemic.

CONCLUSION

After coronavirus infection was identified in China all countries are still battling novel virus variations two years into the pandemic, with the fifth and sixth waves of vaccinations having varying degrees of success in immunizing their national populations. Additionally, by contrasting the effects of foreign travel on the private sector prior to and following COVID-19, this paper examines research questions. The article suggested using qualitative research methodologies as an analytical method to collect data from tourism industry employees. The opinions of the respondents were obtained through online emails for the questionnaire survey, which also took into consideration the desires of people for specific tourist destinations and the arrival of future travelers. In this article active coronavirus cases, number of deaths are analyzed with current data.

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